
REPORT ON VC55 SPIDER STATUS IN THE RUTLAND WATER AREA

2022-SPIDERS-RW-AREA

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Abstract

This report on the local status of spiders in VC55 Spiders has been derived from records held by LRERC (Leicestershire and Rutland Environmental Records Centre) and managed by the ORCA software system.

1 Introduction

This work uses spider records held by LRERC (Leicestershire and Rutland Environmental Records Centre) and managed by the ORCA software system. We are fortunate that the staff curating these records have taken the time to include classifications that link to the original data source and other useful details. This has allowed the recreation of the datasets used in previous publications by Crocker and Daws (2001) and formed solid foundation upon which to base this work.

2 Outline Methodology

Data from ORCA are downloaded as an Excel spreadsheet with the column headings as field names. The R code used in this work is designed to cope with multiple spreadsheets with varying naming conventions so can be adapted to work with many data sources. Taxonomic family data is not included in the ORCA data, which is addressed here by joining the ORCA data with a spider check list (British Arachnological Society 2019) to extend the number of fields with family and a sort code. Recent pitfall trapping results at Rutland Water are also included in this report after combining with the ORCA data. Before processing all duplicates are removed and a sub-set using only records within the area of interest used to produce the species check-list and associated atlas entries.

The VC55 trends have been derived from a network metric called eigencentality using all available data. This metric represents the probability of a species being observed, so it is correlated with occupancy model outputs, which try to measure the proportion of sites where a species is present independent of recorder bias. However, eigencentality is much easier to calculate annually for each species to allow the fitting of linear models. Where the fitting of the model is statistically significant the slope is used to determine if the species is increasing or decreasing. No change is assigned to species where no significant trend was detected by this method, which works better for species with many records. This means that trends are easier to detect in common species with more records. Even with these caveats, it is the opinion of the county recorders for spiders that these results are a useful guide. A CSV file of the check-list is also produced at the same time this document is compiled.

*Thanks to Dr Alan Cann, (Co-County Recorder for Spiders), Leicestershire VC55, and Dr Francesca Mancini, (CEH Knowledge Exchange Project), for their helpful discussions in the preparation of this report.

3 Data Atlas

This analysis considers all the records for VC55, but focusses on those within the bounding box of the map below for special interest. Comments on trends are based on *all* VC55 records, not just those local to this report.

4 Local Check List

Table 1: Spider species of the Rutland Water Area.

ID	family	species	VC55.trend
003	Pholcidae	Pholcus phalangioides	Increasing.
005	Segestriidae	Segestria senoculata	No change.
009	Dysderidae	Dysdera crocata	No change.
014	Mimetidae	Ero cambridgei	No change.
022	Nesticidae	Nesticus cellulanus	No change.
038	Theridiidae	Steatoda bipunctata	Increasing.
042	Theridiidae	Anelosimus vittatus	Increasing.
047	Theridiidae	Parasteatoda lunata	No change.
048	Theridiidae	Parasteatoda tepidariorum	Increasing.
049	Theridiidae	Parasteatoda simulans	No change.
050	Theridiidae	Phylloneta sisypchia	No change.
051	Theridiidae	Phylloneta impressa	No change.
055	Theridiidae	Theridion varians	No change.
058	Theridiidae	Theridion melanurum	No change.
059	Theridiidae	Theridion mystaceum	No change.
060	Theridiidae	Sardinidion blackwalli	No change.
061	Theridiidae	Platnickina tincta	No change.
064	Theridiidae	Paidiscura pallens	No change.
068	Theridiidae	Coleosoma floridanum	No change.
069	Theridiidae	Enoplognatha ovata	No change.

Table 1: Spider species of the Rutland Water Area. (*continued*)

ID	family	species	VC55.trend
075	Theridiidae	Robertus lividus	Decreasing.
085	Linyphiidae	Ceratinella brevis	Decreasing.
086	Linyphiidae	Ceratinella scabrosa	No change.
087	Linyphiidae	Walckenaeria acuminata	Decreasing.
093	Linyphiidae	Walckenaeria atrotibialis	No change.
096	Linyphiidae	Walckenaeria dysderoides	No change.
103	Linyphiidae	Walckenaeria unicornis	Decreasing.
108	Linyphiidae	Dicymbium nigrum	No change.
118	Linyphiidae	Hylyphantes graminicola	No change.
119	Linyphiidae	Gnathonarium dentatum	No change.
122	Linyphiidae	Gongylidium rufipes	No change.
125	Linyphiidae	Hypomma bituberculatum	Decreasing.
127	Linyphiidae	Hypomma cornutum	No change.
135	Linyphiidae	Gonatium rubens	No change.
138	Linyphiidae	Maso sundevalli	No change.
143	Linyphiidae	Pocadicnemis juncea	No change.
145	Linyphiidae	Oedothorax gibbosus	Decreasing.
146	Linyphiidae	Oedothorax fuscus	No change.
148	Linyphiidae	Oedothorax retusus	No change.
149	Linyphiidae	Oedothorax apicatus	Decreasing.
185	Linyphiidae	Monocephalus fuscipes	No change.
187	Linyphiidae	Lophomma punctatum	Decreasing.
188	Linyphiidae	Saloca diceros	No change.
189	Linyphiidae	Gongylidiellum vivum	No change.
192	Linyphiidae	Micrargus herbigradus	Decreasing.
199	Linyphiidae	Erigonella hiemalis	No change.
201	Linyphiidae	Savignia frontata	Decreasing.
202	Linyphiidae	Diplocephalus cristatus	Decreasing.
204	Linyphiidae	Diplocephalus latifrons	No change.
206	Linyphiidae	Diplocephalus picinus	Decreasing.
214	Linyphiidae	Typhochrestus digitatus	No change.
218	Linyphiidae	Erigone dentipalpis	No change.
219	Linyphiidae	Erigone atra	No change.
221	Linyphiidae	Erigone arctica	Decreasing.
228	Linyphiidae	Prinerigone vagans	No change.
254	Linyphiidae	Ostearius melanopygius	No change.
256	Linyphiidae	Porrhomma pygmaeum	Decreasing.
261	Linyphiidae	Porrhomma microphthalmum	No change.
267	Linyphiidae	Agyneta subtilis	No change.
283	Linyphiidae	Microneta viaria	No change.
293	Linyphiidae	Centromerus dilutus	Decreasing.
308	Linyphiidae	Saaristoa abnormis	No change.
312	Linyphiidae	Bathyphantes approximatus	Decreasing.
313	Linyphiidae	Bathyphantes gracilis	No change.
314	Linyphiidae	Bathyphantes parvulus	No change.
315	Linyphiidae	Bathyphantes nigrinus	Decreasing.
317	Linyphiidae	Kaestneria dorsalis	No change.
318	Linyphiidae	Kaestneria pullata	Decreasing.
319	Linyphiidae	Diplostyla concolor	No change.
321	Linyphiidae	Drapetisca socialis	No change.

Table 1: Spider species of the Rutland Water Area. (*continued*)

ID	family	species	VC55.trend
323	Linyphiidae	Floronia bucculenta	No change.
325	Linyphiidae	Labulla thoracica	No change.
331	Linyphiidae	Lepthyphantes leprosus	No change.
332	Linyphiidae	Lepthyphantes minutus	No change.
336	Linyphiidae	Tenuiphantes tenuis	No change.
337	Linyphiidae	Tenuiphantes zimmermanni	Decreasing.
340	Linyphiidae	Tenuiphantes flavipes	Decreasing.
341	Linyphiidae	Tenuiphantes tenebricola	No change.
342	Linyphiidae	Palliduphantes ericaeus	Decreasing.
351	Linyphiidae	Helophora insignis	No change.
353	Linyphiidae	Linyphia triangularis	No change.
354	Linyphiidae	Linyphia hortensis	No change.
355	Linyphiidae	Neriere montana	No change.
356	Linyphiidae	Neriere clathrata	Decreasing.
357	Linyphiidae	Neriere peltata	No change.
361	Linyphiidae	Microlinyphia impigra	Decreasing.
364	Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha extensa	No change.
366	Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha montana	No change.
367	Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha obtusa	No change.
368	Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha nigrita	Decreasing.
370	Tetragnathidae	Pachygnatha clercki	Decreasing.
372	Tetragnathidae	Pachygnatha degeeri	No change.
373	Tetragnathidae	Metellina segmentata	No change.
374	Tetragnathidae	Metellina menzei	No change.
375	Tetragnathidae	Metellina merianae	No change.
380	Araneidae	Araneus diadematus	Increasing.
381	Araneidae	Araneus quadratus	Increasing.
384	Araneidae	Araneus sturmi	No change.
386	Araneidae	Larinioides cornutus	No change.
387	Araneidae	Larinioides sclopetarius	No change.
389	Araneidae	Nuctenea umbratica	Increasing.
392	Araneidae	Araniella cucurbitina	Increasing.
393	Araneidae	Araniella opisthographa	No change.
405	Araneidae	Zygiella atrica	No change.
408	Araneidae	Cyclosa conica	No change.
414	Lycosidae	Pardosa palustris	No change.
415	Lycosidae	Pardosa pullata	No change.
416	Lycosidae	Pardosa prativaga	No change.
417	Lycosidae	Pardosa amentata	No change.
418	Lycosidae	Pardosa nigriceps	No change.
419	Lycosidae	Pardosa lugubris	No change.
420	Lycosidae	Pardosa saltans	No change.
428	Lycosidae	Alopecosa pulverulenta	No change.
432	Lycosidae	Trochosa ruricola	Decreasing.
434	Lycosidae	Trochosa terricola	No change.
441	Lycosidae	Pirata piraticus	No change.
448	Pisauridae	Pisaura mirabilis	Increasing.
453	Agelenidae	Textrix denticulata	No change.
456	Agelenidae	Eratigena duellica	Increasing.
459	Agelenidae	Tegenaria domestica	No change.

Table 1: Spider species of the Rutland Water Area. (*continued*)

ID	family	species	VC55.trend
472	Hahniidae	Hahnia nava	No change.
478	Dictynidae	Dictyna arundinacea	No change.
481	Dictynidae	Dictyna uncinata	No change.
485	Dictynidae	Nigma walckenaeri	No change.
486	Dictynidae	Lathys humilis	No change.
493	Amaurobiidae	Amaurobius fenestralis	No change.
494	Amaurobiidae	Amaurobius similis	Increasing.
495	Amaurobiidae	Amaurobius ferox	Increasing.
496	Anyphaenidae	Anyphaena accentuata	No change.
514	Clubionidae	Clubiona reclusa	No change.
520	Clubionidae	Clubiona pallidula	No change.
521	Clubionidae	Clubiona phragmitis	Decreasing.
524	Clubionidae	Clubiona neglecta	No change.
527	Clubionidae	Clubiona lutescens	No change.
528	Clubionidae	Clubiona compta	No change.
536	Cheiracanthiidae	Cheiracanthium erraticum	Increasing.
543	Gnaphosidae	Drassodes lapidosus	No change.
544	Gnaphosidae	Drassodes cupreus	No change.
552	Gnaphosidae	Scotophaeus blackwalli	Increasing.
572	Gnaphosidae	Micaria pulicaria	No change.
577	Miturgidae	Zora spinimana	No change.
583	Philodromidae	Philodromus dispar	Increasing.
584	Philodromidae	Philodromus aureolus	No change.
586	Philodromidae	Philodromus cespitum	No change.
588	Philodromidae	Philodromus collinus	No change.
600	Philodromidae	Tibellus oblongus	No change.
602	Thomisidae	Diaea dorsata	No change.
605	Thomisidae	Xysticus cristatus	No change.
610	Thomisidae	Xysticus ulmi	No change.
622	Thomisidae	Ozyptila praticola	No change.
627	Salticidae	Salticus scenicus	Increasing.
628	Salticidae	Salticus cingulatus	No change.
644	Salticidae	Euophrys frontalis	No change.

This references the latest BAS Check-list.

5 Pholcidae

ID:003 *Pholcus phalangioides*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

6 Segestriidae

ID:005 *Segestria senoculata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

7 Dysderidae

ID:009 *Dysdera crocata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

8 Mimetidae

ID:014 *Ero cambridgei*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

9 Nesticidae

ID:022 *Nesticus cellulanus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

10 Theridiidae

ID:038 *Steatoda bipunctata*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:042 *Anelosimus vittatus*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:047 *Parasteatoda lunata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:048 *Parasteatoda tepidariorum*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:049 *Parasteatoda simulans*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:050 *Phylloneta sisyphia*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:051 *Phylloneta impressa*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:055 *Theridion varians*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:058 *Theridion melanurum*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:059 *Theridion mystaceum*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:060 *Sardinidion blackwalli*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:061 *Platnickina tincta*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:064 *Paidiscura pallens*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:068 *Coleosoma floridanum*

VC55 status of this species: No change. This species has not been recorded in VC55 since 2001.

ID:069 *Enoplognatha ovata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:075 *Robertus lividus*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

11 Linyphiidae

ID:085 *Ceratinella brevis*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:086 *Ceratinella scabrosa*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:087 *Walckenaeria acuminata*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:093 *Walckenaeria atrotibialis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:096 *Walckenaeria dysderoides*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:103 *Walckenaeria unicornis*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:108 *Dicymbium nigrum*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:118 *Hylyphantes graminicola*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:119 *Gnathonarium dentatum*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:122 *Gongylidium rufipes*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:125 *Hypomma bituberculatum*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:127 *Hypomma cornutum*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:135 *Gonatium rubens*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:138 *Maso sundevalli*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:143 *Pocadicnemis juncea*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:145 *Oedothorax gibbosus*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:146 *Oedothorax fuscus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:148 *Oedothorax retusus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:149 *Oedothorax apicatus*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:185 *Monocephalus fuscipes*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:187 *Lophomma punctatum*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:188 *Saloca diceros*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:189 *Gongylidiellum vivum*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:192 *Micrargus herbigradus*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:199 *Erigonella hiemalis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:201 *Savignia frontata*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:202 *Diplocephalus cristatus*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:204 *Diplocephalus latifrons*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:206 *Diplocephalus picinus*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:214 *Typhochrestus digitatus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:218 *Erigone dentipalpis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:219 *Erigone atra*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:221 *Erigone arctica*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing. This species has not been recorded in VC55 since 2001.

ID:228 *Prinerigone vagans*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:254 *Ostearius melanopygius*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:256 *Porrhomma pygmaeum*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:261 *Porrhomma microphthalmum*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:267 *Agyneta subtilis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:283 *Microneta viaria*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:293 *Centromerus dilutus*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:308 *Saaristoa abnormis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:312 *Bathyphantes approximatus*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:313 *Bathyphantes gracilis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:314 *Bathyphantes parvulus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:315 *Bathyphantes nigrinus*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:317 *Kaestneria dorsalis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:318 *Kaestneria pullata*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:319 *Diplostyla concolor*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:321 *Drapetisca socialis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:323 *Floronia bucculenta*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:325 *Labulla thoracica*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:331 *Lepthyphantes leprosus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:332 *Lepthyphantes minutus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:336 *Tenuiphantes tenuis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:337 *Tenuiphantes zimmermanni*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:340 *Tenuiphantes flavipes*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:341 *Tenuiphantes tenebricola*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:342 *Palliduphantes ericaeus*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:351 *Helophora insignis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:353 *Linyphia triangularis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:354 *Linyphia hortensis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:355 *Neriene montana*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:356 *Neriene clathrata*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:357 *Neriene peltata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:361 *Microlinyphia impigra*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

12 Tetragnathidae

ID:364 *Tetragnatha extensa*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:366 *Tetragnatha montana*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:367 *Tetragnatha obtusa*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:368 *Tetragnatha nigrita*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:370 *Pachygnatha clercki*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:372 *Pachygnatha degeeri*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:373 *Metellina segmentata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:374 *Metellina menzei*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:375 *Metellina merianae*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

13 Araneidae

ID:380 *Araneus diadematus*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:381 *Araneus quadratus*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:384 *Araneus sturmi*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:386 *Larinioides cornutus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:387 *Larinioides sclopetarius*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:389 *Nuctenea umbratica*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:392 *Araniella cucurbitina*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:393 *Araniella opisthographa*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:405 *Zygiella atrica*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:408 *Cyclosa conica*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

14 Lycosidae

ID:414 *Pardosa palustris*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:415 *Pardosa pullata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:416 *Pardosa prativaga*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:417 *Pardosa amentata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:418 *Pardosa nigriceps*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:419 *Pardosa lugubris*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:420 *Pardosa saltans*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:428 *Alopecosa pulverulenta*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:432 *Trochosa ruricola*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:434 *Trochosa terricola*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:441 *Pirata piraticus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

15 Pisauridae

ID:448 *Pisaura mirabilis*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

16 Agelenidae

ID:453 *Textrix denticulata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:456 *Eratigena duellica*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:459 *Tegenaria domestica*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

17 Hahniidae

ID:472 *Hahnia nava*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

18 Dictynidae

ID:478 *Dictyna arundinacea*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:481 *Dictyna uncinata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:485 *Nigma walckenaeri*

VC55 status of this species: No change. This species is new to VC55 since 2000.

ID:486 *Lathys humilis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

19 Amaurobiidae

ID:493 *Amaurobius fenestralis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:494 *Amaurobius similis*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:495 *Amaurobius ferox*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

20 Anyphaenidae

ID:496 *Anyphaena accentuata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

21 Clubionidae

ID:514 *Clubiona reclusa*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:520 *Clubiona pallidula*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:521 *Clubiona phragmitis*

VC55 status of this species: Decreasing.

ID:524 *Clubiona neglecta*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:527 *Clubiona lutescens*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:528 *Clubiona comta*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

22 Cheiracanthiidae

ID:536 *Cheiracanthium erraticum*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

23 Gnaphosidae

ID:543 *Drassodes lapidosus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:544 *Drassodes cupreus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:552 *Scotophaeus blackwalli*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:572 *Micaria pulicaria*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

24 Miturgidae

ID:577 *Zora spinimana*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

25 Philodromidae

ID:583 *Philodromus dispar*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:584 *Philodromus aureolus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:586 *Philodromus cespitum*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:588 *Philodromus collinus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:600 *Tibellus oblongus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

26 Thomisidae

ID:602 *Diaea dorsata*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:605 *Xysticus cristatus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:610 *Xysticus ulmi*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:622 *Ozyptila praticola*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

27 Salticidae

ID:627 *Salticus scenicus*

VC55 status of this species: Increasing.

ID:628 *Salticus cingulatus*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

ID:644 *Euophrys frontalis*

VC55 status of this species: No change.

References

- British Arachnological Society. 2019. "2019 GBI Spider checklist."
- Crocker, John, and Jonathan. Daws. 2001. *Spiders of Leicestershire & Rutland : millennium atlas*. Loughborough: Loughborough Naturalists' Club in association with Kairos.